

EPOS
ERIC

EPOS
VISUAL IDENTITY
MANUAL

EP**S**
EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

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VISUAL IDENTITY
MANUAL**

Federica Tanlongo, Barbara Angioni

Version 2.0 | December 2023

This document builds on EPOS Identity Manual 1.0, 2022, by E. Balli, B. Angioni, R. Silva, S. Filosa

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Introduction: the EPOS Visual Identity

Visual identity is much more than the Infrastructure's logo: it labels everything that EPOS communicates to the outside world and represents its visual personality. The Infrastructure's identity allows it to be recognised both within and outside, by transmitting EPOS values in an emotive manner.

Why is it important to organise and formalise EPOS's visual identity? By establishing and communicating a clear and comprehensive graphic identity we can ensure that the name EPOS is associated with the internationality, credibility and scientific level that the Infrastructure stands for.

A professional approach to visual identity allows us to create information material avoiding any graphic ambiguity or interpretations based on personal taste and skill, which could overshadow or even undermine EPOS's brand identity.

This handbook contains some prescriptive rules on the use of the logo, typeface, colour palette, and graphic elements, as well as advice and guidelines to protect the brand identity that EPOS is delineating.

The document was developed by examining the material produced between 2019 and 2021 and by distinguishing the core elements of EPOS's brand identity from those that might generate confusion, and adding further elements to refine the brand identity.

EPOS's identity must be consistent over time, but it must also adapt to structural, stylistic and technological changes, as well as to improvements suggested by its users. For this reason, the guidelines contained in the present handbook should be revised every two-three years.

This handbook has been produced by EPOS Communication Office.

The logo

Logo Core Elements

The primary EPOS logo represents the overarching brand and should be used on official documents, websites, and communications related to EPOS as a whole. It consists of the full name "EPOS" with the tagline "European Plate Observing System".

The logo consists of the combination of an icon and text: the EPOS acronym with a circle containing the map of Europe representing the letter O, and the spelled-out acronym European Plate Observing System. These elements are inseparable and only their size (maintaining the proportions) and colours may be modified, depending on the different applications described in this handbook. The logo must always be reproduced by using the original file - with file extensions png or jpg - available in the restricted access area of the EPOS website (www.epos-eu.org).

Colours

The logo comes in three variants:

- Standard in two colours (GREEN Pantone Solid Coated 553 C, YELLOW Pantone Solid Coated 124 C) to be used on a white background (A);
- a black-only version to be applied against light or intermediate backgrounds (B);
- the negative version for use on dark backgrounds (C, D, E, F).

A

B

C

D

E

F

Improper Uses

There are some basic rules for the correct reproduction of the EPOS logo:

1. the logo cannot have different colours from the official ones;
2. dark backgrounds require the negative logo to be used;
3. different versions of the logo should not be used together on the same page/material.

Logo Safety Margins and Exceptions

Not only should the logo be placed in a position that ensures its proper visibility but no icons or text should be placed around it that could reduce its impact. To this end, a safety margin, equal at least to the height of the letter E contained in the logo, must be maintained around the logo on all its sides.

Logo Size

The EPOS logo should be applied on all official material. It is therefore important to maintain its visibility irrespective of the utilised media.

Therefore, we have identified a minimum threshold size and a series of reference sizes to be adopted when using the most common formats; no limitation is imposed on large-size formats.

It is important not to alter the original proportions of the logo and to use as a minimum reference size the one of the closest standard format (e.g., for an A2 format the logo should be at least 7 cm in width; for an A6 – and all smaller formats – it should be 1.6 cm in width).

Width minimum size: 1,6 cm

A5: 2 cm

A4: 3 cm

A3: 5 cm

Logo Positioning

To ensure some degree of uniformity to all EPOS material, there are four possible positions for the logo: at the top and bottom along the vertical bisecting line of the page or in the upper corners.

These rules do not apply to letter-headed paper which follows its own rules (see page 25).

Size and margins

A5

logo: width 2 cm

upper margin: 1.5 cm

lower margin: 1 cm

side margins: never below 1 cm

A4

logo: width 3 cm

upper margin: 2.5cm

lower margin: 1.5 cm

side margins: never below 1.5 cm

A3

logo: width 5 cm

upper margin: 4 cm

lower margin: 2 cm

side margins: never below 2 cm

Family branding

EPOS is a complex environment and includes many different actors and identities. In particular, the national components, generally grouped in Joint Research Units, and the TCS are not only pivotal elements in the EPOS architecture, but also subjects that have a substantial autonomy in organising, executing and communicating their work.

Family branding is a strategic approach to create a unified visual identity for various entities within the EPOS Research Infrastructure, including the national National Nodes and TCS. The aim is to offer a practical branding tool to National Nodes and TCS to communicate their individuality while also reasserting their belonging to the EPOS RI as a whole.

Family branding can also be extended to additional elements, such as specific services and activities. This action is always agreed and carried out under the supervision of the communication office.

National EPOS logos

Each national branch (e.g. EPOS-France, EPOS-UK) can have its own logo, which incorporates the EPOS brand identity. The logo is composed of the EPOS the logotype – always complete – and the Alpha2 ISO Country Code in upper case typeface aligned horizontally to the logo.

TCS logos

Thematic Core Services are individual communities within EPOS (e.g., Seismology, Volcano Observations). Each TCS logo includes a unique icon that represents the specific theme (for example, a wave icon for Tsunami) and has its distinctive colour, which is part of the EPOS' secondary colour palette.

The logo is completed by the full TCS name. Three variations are allowed, depending on the context where the logo is used: name under the logo, name around the logo and name and icon combined with the EPOS logotype.

Logos should be legible and identifiable at different sizes. In addition, Logo safety margins rules should apply to TCS logos as well as to the EPOS main logo. They are scalable at need, provided they look good and remain identifiable whether they are displayed on a large banner or a small business card.

Family branding and templates

The EPOS family branding involves not only logos, but also the specific templates to be used in different communication activities. The family branding templates are discussed later in the document.

Availability of logos, formats and specific requests

The Communication Office is responsible for the production of the EPOS logo, country logos and TCS logos. Partners can find the official logos in different sizes and formats on the EPOS intranet:

<https://repository.epos-eu.org/index.php/apps/files/?dir=/Shared%20Folder/Logos&fileid=89351> and on the EPOS website. Should additional formats be needed for specific uses, these can be requested by sending a message to the Communication Office at: communication-office@lists.epos-eu.org

Use with additional Logos

Where the EPOS logo is used in conjunction with other logos (e.g. EPOS Events, initiatives organised in conjunction with other partners, etc), these should be aligned horizontally to the EPOS logo when they are centred on the page or, alternatively, placed in the diagonally opposite corner of the page.

For EPOS events, the additional logo should always be placed at the foot of the page, so as to leave the EPOS logo in a dominant position.

These guidelines apply to logos of activities that are directly related to EPOS. External logos, such as sponsorships, collaborations, etc., should be placed horizontally in one or more rows at the bottom of the page (below the EPOS logo).

Examples of proper use with multiple logos

The graphics below are intended to exemplify the proper use of different logos in complex scenarios.

In case of events involving different stakeholders (e.g. TCS, National Node, event hosting organisations and/or other partners, it is important to always include the EPOS logo, the National Node's and/or the TCS' logo(s), as well as those of other involved parties.

In example n° 1 (left), an event organised by EPOS-SE and TCS-AH, the hosting organisation is first, with national node and TCS logos following and additional partners in the right side of the line. The EPOS main logo is included in the header. In the second example (right), A national node's Kick-off, the EPOS-SE logo is in the header, and the other logos (including the main EPOS logo) are in the footer.

There are no strict prescriptions in the order of the logos, but designers should take into account the level of involvement of the partners. If in doubt, the Communication Office can be contacted for advice on the subject.

Scientific Workshop on Mining & Post-Mining Seismicity

PROGRAM

Wednesday September 20

Welcome and opening	08:00 - 08:30	Registration & Welcome
	08:30 - 08:40	Opening Speech by S. Dineva (LTU), B. Orlecka (IGPAS)
	08:40 - 09:00	Opening Speeches by EPOS-Sweden and PostMineQuake project representatives
Morning session Convener: Emmanuelle Klein	09:00 - 09:30	Induced seismicity in Kirunaavaara mine – overview and challenges by C. Dahner and S. Dineva
	09:30 - 10:00	Study of mining induced seismicity with various observation techniques (EPOS-MUSE 2 episode, Upper Silesia, Poland) by G. Murlik & A. Kozłuba
	10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break
	10:30 - 11:00	Bringing new knowledge on the mechanics of deformation and on seismic hazard inside in Garpenberg mine using innovative optical instruments by J. Kinscher & P. Bernard
	11:00 - 11:30	Passive Tomography results for mines in Sweden (Kirunaavaara and Garpenberg mines) by N. Fiara Agostinetti, S. Dineva, G. Taylor, A. Tryggvasson
	11:30 - 12:00	Afterstock study of the larger seismic events in Kirunaavaara and Malmberget mines (Sweden) by D. Gospodárov, K. Jonsson, C. Dahner, S. Dineva
	12:00 - 13:00	Lunch
	13:30 - 14:00	Study of surface deformations in the area of post-mining seismicity (case study, Upper Silesian Coal Basin, Poland) by V. Sokola-Szewiolo, Z. Szejka & M. Pomykaj
	14:00 - 14:30	Case study of the post-mining seismicity of the former coal basin of Gardanne (France) by J. Contrucci, J. Kinscher, S. Cesca, P. Niemez & P. Dominique
	14:30 - 15:00	Post-mining seismicity during flooding of coal Kazimierz-Juliusz mine, Poland by A. Kozłuba & G. Murlik
15:00 - 15:30	Coffee Break	
15:30 - 16:00	Relation Between Seismicity and Stress Changes in Underground Mine: From Research Challenges to Practical Tools (Vimova Project for Four Mines in Sweden) by S. Dineva and C. Dahner	
16:00 - 16:30	3D Elastodynamic Modelling Applied to Complex Blasting Problems by L. Linzer	
16:30 - 17:00	Initial experience with the newly created system for monitoring the dynamics of surface changes during the transition to the post-mining phase by M. Kajzar & E. Jirankova	
19:00	Social Diner	

EPOS Sweden Kick-Off

Virtual event, 13th September 2023, 09:30 - 12:00

Är du intresserad av geovetenskapligt data från hela Europa? Jordbävningar i Grönland, landhöjning i Skandinavien, magnetiskt data från X eller Y-data från Z? The European Plate Observing System (EPOS) är en forskningsinfrastruktur som tillhandahåller just det. EPOS Sverige bjuder in till en förmiddag med information - vad EPOS är, hur EPOS kan utnyttjas i forskning och hur just du kan ta del av EPOS.

The European Plate Observing System (EPOS) is the single, genuinely pan-European distributed research infrastructure for data and data services related to studies of the solid Earth. The new EPOS data portal, launched in April 2023, provides homogenised FAIR data and services about the solid Earth. It facilitates open access to multidisciplinary, trans-national data through a single access point. EPOS users can explore and combine data sets in new ways, and use them for innovative science or a wealth of other purposes, from basic research to applied Earth sciences.

EPOS Sweden is inviting you to a morning dedicated to EPOS and its data portal. We will explain the EPOS research infrastructure and how it works. We will demonstrate how EPOS can be utilised for your research and show how you can get involved.

Join us via Zoom at
<https://lulea.se/room/94/55389481995>
 7th September 2023, 09:30 - 12:00

Programme

- 09:30 - 09:40 Welcome and summary in Swedish
- 09:40 - 10:10 The European Plate Observing System (EPOS)
- 10:10 - 10:40 Thematic communities in EPOS (Thematic Core Services, TCS)
- 10:40 - 10:50 Break
- 10:50 - 11:35 Demonstration cases
- 11:35 - 12:00 Questions and discussions

For more information on EPOS, please visit www.epos-se.se (EPOS Sweden) and www.epos-eric.eu (EPOS).

EPOS is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EPOS-ERIC). EPOS Sweden is a national research infrastructure that operates the Swedish contribution to EPOS-ERIC. EPOS Sweden is supported by the participating organisations and the Swedish Research Council. The Swedish membership in EPOS-ERIC is managed and funded by the Swedish Research Council.

Colours

Colour Palettes

Primary palette

The palette of the EPOS logo is composed of the two colours featured in the logo: Green and Yellow. These are distinctive colours of the EPOS brand identity which, however, don't represent the predominant colour spectrum of its graphics, as they should be instantly identified with the logo.

EPOS LOGO COLOURS	C %	M %	Y %	K %	R	G	B	H°	S %	B %	#	PANTONE SOLID COATED
YELLOW	0	37	94	10	229	145	14	36	94	90	d49f2a	124 C
GREEN	80	33	85	60	21	44	21	120	52	17	152c15	553 C

Secondary palettes

The 30 colours of the secondary palettes are inspired to the colours of the logo. The colours go well with those of the primary palette, allowing for optimal contrast between text and background. Ideal colour matches have also been studied by identifying the colours that best match those of the secondary palettes, to be used for the various media containing graphics.

PANTONE SOLID COATED RGB CMYK #		
7485 C 210 220 187 25 6 34 0 d2dcbb	617 C 187 179 101 30 22 73 6 bbb365	7746 C 152 153 61 45 27 96 11 98993d
545 C 202 216 229 28 9 8 0 cad8e5	7703 C 79 152 188 84 20 19 2 4f98bc	7713 C 15 122 136 100 25 41 14 0f7a88
7681 C 152 166 49 31 9 0 98a6c9	7456 C 99 109 174 73 60 0 0 636dae	7687 C 46 68 134 100 81 13 2 2e4486
5215 C 166 148 163 35 43 24 5 a694a3	7646 C 153 109 133 36 64 28 10 996d85	4985 C 122 77 83 33 71 48 35 7a4d53
677 C 222 203 218 11 25 7 0 dectbda	680 C 188 147 177 24 51 13 0 bc93b1	682 C 137 73 117 42 83 25 10 894975
487 C 220 165 147 6 45 41 0 dca593	7416 C 206 104 84 5 73 70 0 ce6854	1797 C 168 54 60 14 94 80 4 b2363c
7506 C 235 217 178 8 16 36 0 ebd9b2	7508 C 213 182 128 13 31 57 3 d5b680	1255 C 162 131 46 27 42 98 19 a2832e
Cool Gray 1 C 215 215 213 18 13 15 0 d7d7d5	Cool Gray 6 C 166 166 168 37 28 28 7 a8a6a8	Cool Gray 9 C 117 118 121 53 42 39 23 757679
5315 C 214 213 221 18 15 9 0 d6d5dd	442 C 161 170 169 42 24 30 6 a1aaa9	444 C 114 123 123 57 38 41 22 727b7b
7534 C 206 202 188 21 17 27 2 cecabc	401 C 172 167 158 33 28 34 8 aca79e	416 C 125 126 115 49 37 47 23 7d7e73

ON EPOS YELLOW PANTONE SOLID COATED RGB CMYK #		
7485 C 210 220 187 25 6 34 0 d2dcbb	617 C 187 179 101 30 22 73 6 bbb365	7746 C 152 153 61 45 27 96 11 98993d
545 C 202 216 229 28 9 8 0 cad8e5	7703 C 79 152 188 84 20 19 2 4f98bc	7713 C 15 122 136 100 25 41 14 0f7a88
7681 C 152 166 49 31 9 0 98a6c9	7456 C 99 109 174 73 60 0 0 636dae	7687 C 46 68 134 100 81 13 2 2e4486
5215 C 166 148 163 35 43 24 5 a694a3	7646 C 153 109 133 36 64 28 10 996d85	4985 C 122 77 83 33 71 48 35 7a4d53
677 C 222 203 218 11 25 7 0 dectbda	680 C 188 147 177 24 51 13 0 bc93b1	682 C 137 73 117 42 83 25 10 894975
487 C 220 165 147 6 45 41 0 dca593	7416 C 206 104 84 5 73 70 0 ce6854	1797 C 168 54 60 14 94 80 4 b2363c
7506 C 235 217 178 8 16 36 0 ebd9b2	7508 C 213 182 128 13 31 57 3 d5b680	1255 C 162 131 46 27 42 98 19 a2832e
Cool Gray 1 C 215 215 213 18 13 15 0 d7d7d5	Cool Gray 6 C 166 166 168 37 28 28 7 a8a6a8	Cool Gray 9 C 117 118 121 53 42 39 23 757679
5315 C 214 213 221 18 15 9 0 d6d5dd	442 C 161 170 169 42 24 30 6 a1aaa9	444 C 114 123 123 57 38 41 22 727b7b
7534 C 206 202 188 21 17 27 2 cecabc	401 C 172 167 158 33 28 34 8 aca79e	416 C 125 126 115 49 37 47 23 7d7e73

ON EPOS GREEN PANTONE SOLID COATED RGB CMYK #		
7485 C 210 220 187 25 6 34 0 d2dcbb	617 C 187 179 101 30 22 73 6 bbb365	7746 C 152 153 61 45 27 96 11 98993d
545 C 202 216 229 28 9 8 0 cad8e5	7703 C 79 152 188 84 20 19 2 4f98bc	7713 C 15 122 136 100 25 41 14 0f7a88
7681 C 152 166 49 31 9 0 98a6c9	7456 C 99 109 174 73 60 0 0 636dae	7687 C 46 68 134 100 81 13 2 2e4486
5215 C 166 148 163 35 43 24 5 a694a3	7646 C 153 109 133 36 64 28 10 996d85	4985 C 122 77 83 33 71 48 35 7a4d53
677 C 222 203 218 11 25 7 0 dectbda	680 C 188 147 177 24 51 13 0 bc93b1	682 C 137 73 117 42 83 25 10 894975
487 C 220 165 147 6 45 41 0 dca593	7416 C 206 104 84 5 73 70 0 ce6854	1797 C 168 54 60 14 94 80 4 b2363c
7506 C 235 217 178 8 16 36 0 ebd9b2	7508 C 213 182 128 13 31 57 3 d5b680	1255 C 162 131 46 27 42 98 19 a2832e
Cool Gray 1 C 215 215 213 18 13 15 0 d7d7d5	Cool Gray 6 C 166 166 168 37 28 28 7 a8a6a8	Cool Gray 9 C 117 118 121 53 42 39 23 757679
5315 C 214 213 221 18 15 9 0 d6d5dd	442 C 161 170 169 42 24 30 6 a1aaa9	444 C 114 123 123 57 38 41 22 727b7b
7534 C 206 202 188 21 17 27 2 cecabc	401 C 172 167 158 33 28 34 8 aca79e	416 C 125 126 115 49 37 47 23 7d7e73

TCS distinctive colours

The main reference colour system used by EPOS is the CMYK four-colour process and the following tables show the distinctive EPOS colours in the dark and light variants.

Dark

TCS ICONS & VISUALS COLOURS	C %	M %	Y %	K %
SEISMOLOGY	64	34	62	30
NFO	84	100	56	0
GNSS	46	90	0	0
VOLCANO	5	100	85	0
SATELLITE	100	0	38	0
GEOMAG	100	98	16	0
AH	80	15	0	0
GIM	0	80	80	0
MSL	75	0	75	10
TSUNAMI	44	2	10	25

Light

TCS ICONS & VISUALS COLOURS	C %	M %	Y %	K %
SEISMOLOGY	50	29	47	12
NFO	51	65	31	15
GNSS	33	63	0	0
VOLCANO	0	70	59	0
SATELLITE	70	0	30	0
GEOMAG	69	61	16	0
AH	56	10	0	0
GIM	0	56	56	0
MSL	46	0	50	0
TSUNAMI	57	18	24	3

In cases when it is not possible to use CMYK as a reference system, derivative colours, described with the Pantone, RGB, HSB and HTML colour matching systems, can be used instead. The following tables show the derivative colour codes corresponding to the main EPOS distinctive colours. Note that the difference in colour reference system may result in small differences with the main colours, however these differences are considered acceptable,

Derivative colours - dark

TCS ICONS & VISUALS COLOURS	R	G	B	H°	S %	B %	#	PANTONE SOLID COATED
SEISMOLOGY	87	113	89	125	2	44	577159	5615 C
NFO	84	45	84	299	47	33	542d54	262 C
GNSS	157	53	139	310	66	62	9d358b	513 C
VOLCANO	221	12	41	352	95	87	dd0c29	186 C
SATELLITE	0	155	167	185	100	66	009ba7	320 C
GEOMAG	47	44	120	243	64	47	2f2c78	2685 C
AH	0	160	222	197	100	87	00a0de	299 C
GIM	233	79	53	9	77	92	e94f35	7417 C
MSL	45	160	95	146	72	63	2da05f	7739 C
TSUNAMI	82	159	170	188	52	67	529faa	7709 C

Derivative colours - light

TCS ICONS & VISUALS COLOURS	R	G	B	H°	S %	B %	#	PANTONE SOLID COATED
SEISMOLOGY	134	148	131	108	12	58	869483	5497 C
NFO	132	94	122	316	29	52	845e7a	5205 C
GNSS	181	116	175	306	36	71	b574af	514 C
VOLCANO	237	106	92	6	61	92	ed6a5c	7418 C
SATELLITE	49	183	188	182	74	74	31b7bc	319 C
GEOMAG	103	104	156	239	34	61	67689c	2725 C
AH	114	189	234	203	51	92	72bdea	2915 C
GIM	241	139	108	14	55	95	f18b6c	1635 C
MSL	154	204	154	120	25	80	9acc9a	7478 C
TSUNAMI	117	171	185	192	36	72	95bbc7	550 C

Typography

EPOS Typefaces

Lato and Open Sans are the two typefaces that EPOS decided to adopt for its communications.

They were chosen for their high level of essentiality, legibility, and resolution.

Open Sans is also generally considered among top 10 dyslexia-friendly fonts, thus its choice also serves the practical purpose of being as inclusive as possible when presenting EPOS to readers.

Although both Open Sans and Lato are sans serif typefaces, the difference in weight and geometry is sufficiently pronounced to ensure rhythm and contrast to the composition.

The line spacing for documents / publications should be 1.4. The text should never be justified or hyphenated.

Lato

This typeface should be used for printed materials, including letters, flyers, brochures etc.

Lato Regular		
ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz	0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)
<i>Italic</i>		
ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz	0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)
Bold		
ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz	0123456789
(?!@#\$\$%&*)		
<i>Bold Italic</i>		
ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz	0123456789
(?!@#\$\$%&*)		

Open Sans

This typeface should be used for the website, multimedia presentations or as a replacement for the Lato typeface should these be unavailable.

Open Sans Regular		
ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ	abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz	0123456789
(?!@#\$\$%&*)		

Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)

Bold

**ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789
(?!@#\$\$%&*)**

Bold Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)

To enhance ease of use of the fonts, they are embedded in the official EPOS templates wherever possible, but users should double-check against accidental changes in the font when using official EPOS templates. In any case, users are strongly advised to install the Lato and Open Sans fonts on their device prior to using the templates.

Calibri

Only in case the Lato and Open Sans fonts are not available, it is acceptable to use the Calibri font instead.

Calibri Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)

Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&)*

Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)

Bold Italic

ABCDEFGHIJKIMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 0123456789 (?!@#\$\$%&*)

Graphic Elements

How to handle Images

Photographs have more than a merely decorative or explanatory function, they are an integral component of EPOS aesthetic style.

In view of this, we set up a photo library to be used for the EPOS informational material.

The use of one's own photographs is discouraged.

Photographs from the EPOS library should not be digitally manipulated. It is, however, possible to convert them to black and white or use one of the colours of the official palettes as the dominant tone.

EPOS
EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

ABOUT EPOS ▾ PARTNERS ▾ SERVICES ▾ PROJECTS ▾ COMMUNICATION ▾

Home / Communication

BROCHURES VIDEOS PRESENTATIONS PHOTO GALLERY

Photo Gallery

tectonics
earthquakes
volcanic eruptions
EPOS
georesources
sustainability geodetics
EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

EPOS European Plate Observing System

EARTH TECHNOLOGY ERIC

EPOS at Earth Tech Expo Florence 2021

EPOS-ERIC Launch Cerimony 2018

EPOS WP15 BRGM pictures

Complex plume by Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO)

GSO Guided tour to Solfatara site(2)

PNG and JPEG are acceptable image formats to use on the website. PNG files are high-quality formats and offer a variety of transparency levels, but are relatively heavier. JPEG files are the most commonly used format for images and digital photography and they are faster to load; the file quality, however, is lower than that of the PNG files and they do not support transparency.

Where the images are needed to produce printed material, the high-resolution version of the file (300 dpi) must be used. These are generally available on the EPOS intranet, or, for the appointed communication contacts, on Canva; users are very welcome to contact the Communication Office (communication@epos-eric.eu) if they are unable to find the High Resolution version of a specific picture.

Icons

The TCS icons and/or logos should accompany all TCS-related materials. The icons consist of a graphic representation of each Thematic Core Service inside a circle.

Templates

Templates play a vital role in maintaining a consistent and professional visual identity for EPOS Research Infrastructure and its family branding, such as country National Nodes and thematic core services. By providing pre-defined structures and layouts, templates cater for brand consistency and recognition, and visual cohesion in the creation of specific materials (e.g. official letters, presentations, leaflets, posters), while allowing users to save time and obtain professional materials and ensure that the produced materials reflect EPOS' image accurately and effectively.

Templates are provided to all EPOS partners for the main EPOS identity as well as for the family branding. General EPOS templates should be always used when presenting EPOS

as a whole (e.g. when giving a presentation about EPOS at a conference), while the use of family branding templates is advised when presenting activities/aspects that mainly concern a specific country or TCS. Both include designated spaces for key elements (e.g. logo, contact information, and headings), which are intended to favour clarity of message and ensure that the intended audience can quickly identify important information and the EPOS family's affiliation.

The Communication Office is responsible for the production and update of the EPOS main template and family brand templates. All general use templates (e.g. slides, documents) can be found on the EPOS intranet:

<https://repository.epos-eu.org/index.php/apps/files/?dir=/Shared%20Folder/Templates&fileid=69004>

Multimedia

Presentations and videos

Coherence in the use of EPOS ' brand image also applies to multimedia tools. For example, presentations for the public (e.g. Keynote or Powerpoint) should be prepared using the official templates posted in the restricted section of the EPOS website.

The template comes in two variants: the “plain” one and the one with the European Commission flag and disclaimer, to be used for the EU-funded projects.

Colour variants may be freely used for the creation of diagrams and graphs, choosing them from one of the official palettes. The typeface is Open Sans, preferably with a size of 44 points for titles, 24 for text and 12 for notes.

All official videos should start with an introductory frame containing the EPOS logo in the standard two colours placed at the centre of the screen against a white background, with a fade-in and fade-out effect lasting 5 seconds altogether.

Any other text (e.g., the training title) should be written in EPOS Green or EPOS Yellow Open Sans typeface against a white background.

Letter-headed Paper

There are two possible types of letter-headed paper (legal letter, informal letter) with the EPOS logo. Both versions come with or without the header. The first is better suited to document cover pages or documents with small amounts of text, whereas the plain white version without the header should be preferred for documents containing large amounts of text or many pages. The EPOS contact details are at the bottom of the page.

Branding central

Alongside general templates (e.g. slides, documents, visit cards...) that can be used by all EPOS partners, the Communication Office has created a set of resources intended for people who are involved in communication activities and are familiar with graphic design and page composition.

These resources are only available to professionals appointed by a National Nodes or a TCS and are intended to streamline the production of Country-specific or TCS-specific information and communications materials, such as leaflets, brochures, postcards, graphics optimised for social media etc.

A specific area was created on the EPOS Canva space with brand kits and templates for each TCS and each National Nodes.

The screenshot displays the Canva Brand Kit interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Canva logo, a search bar with the text "Use 5+ words to describ", and a "Create a design" button. Below the navigation bar, the main content area is titled "Brand Kit" and includes an "Add new" button. On the left side, there is a sidebar with a "Back to Home" link and two menu items: "Brand Kit" (selected) and "Brand Templates". The main area shows three brand kit cards, each featuring the EPOS logo (a globe with the letters "EPOS" and "EUROPEANPLATEOBSERVINGSYSTEM" below it) and a color bar at the bottom. The cards are labeled "Kit EPOS-IT JRU", "Kit TCS GNSS", and "Kit TCS MSL".

Each brand kit includes logos, colours, fonts, photo, graphics and icons that are part of the brand and can be used in the creation of a specific material.

The screenshot displays the Canva Brand Kit interface for the 'EPOS communications team'. The interface is organized into several sections:

- Navigation:** Includes a sidebar with 'Back to Brand', 'Kit EPOS-IT NRi', and various asset categories like Logos, Colours, Fonts, Brand voice, Photos, Graphics, and Icons.
- Logos (4):** A section containing four logo variants: 'EPOS_logo.png' (Image · 21 days ago), 'EPOS_LOGO_bianco_ma...' (Image · 29 days ago), another 'EPOS_LOGO_bianco_ma...' (Image · 29 days ago), and 'EPOS_Italia_logo.png' (Image · 5 months ago).
- Colours (3):** A section titled 'Colori di EPOS' with three color swatches: a dark green swatch (#364738), a mustard yellow swatch (#d4a220), and a white swatch (#ffffff). Below this is a 'Colour palette' section with an 'Add new' button.
- Fonts:** A section listing various text styles: Title, Subtitle, Heading, Subheading, Section header, Body, Quote, and Caption. Each style has an edit icon and a trash icon. A link for 'Manage uploaded fonts' is also present.
- Other Sections:** Includes 'Brand voice', 'Photos (0)', 'Graphics (0)', and 'Icons (0)', each with an 'Add new' button.
- Footer:** Contains an 'Invite members' button and a 'Trash' icon.

Canva Design spotlight Business Education Use 5+ words to describe Create a design

KIT TCS GNSS

Brand Kit shared with: EPOS communications team + Add to a folder

← Back to Brand

KIT TCS GNSS

- Logos
- Colours
- Fonts
- Brand voice
- Photos
- Graphics
- Icons

Logos (6) + Add new

- EPOS_logo.png**
Image · 21 days ago
- GNSS name around.png**
Image · 21 days ago
- GNSS name under.png**
Image · 21 days ago
- QRCode_20210802_17A...**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS icone_fullname.p...**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS full name.png**
Image · 5 months ago

Colours (4) + Add new

Colori di GNSS.png

- #883888
- #cd2d2d
- #ffffff
- #000000
- + Add new

Colour palette

- + Add new

Fonts + Add new

Brand voice

Photos (0) + Add new

Graphics (6) + Add new

- Epos_TCS-ICIS_impleme...**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS_postcard.png**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS_postcard 1.png**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS_postcard 2.png**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS_postcard 3.png**
Image · 5 months ago
- GNSS_postcard 4.png**
Image · 5 months ago

Icons (2) + Add new

- GNSS 2.png**
Image · just now
- GNSS 1.png**
Image · just now

In addition, each template kit offers templates for commonly used formats (e.g. leaflet, postcard, poster...), ready to be personalised by adding text and specific images.

The application is set to encourage communication people from National Nodes and TSC to ask for the approval of the Communication Office before printing. This approval process is not mandatory but it is strongly advised, in order to ensure brand consistency and receive advice on the most effective usage of the branding.

Merchandising

The EPOS merchandising products should bear the complete logo (in two colours, white against dark backgrounds or black against light backgrounds).

Products examples

For the production of branded merchandising with a very small print area (e.g. some pens or other small stationery items), where the rendering of the logo may not be optimal, the use of the URL www.epos-eu.org only and/or the full name EPOS - European Plate Observing System is allowed, using one of the 2 main EPOS colours if possible.

Family branding and merchandising

The production of merchandising with the TCS branding is not only allowed, but encouraged in order to increase the recognisability of the family brands, especially in case of events dedicated to a specific community, and, for TCS events, to support the feeling of belonging (e.g. through wearing a t-shirt or a pin identifying oneself with a member of the community). The same applies to the national nodes' family branding.

As for other uses of the EPOS main brand and family branding, communication people from National Nodes and TSC are encouraged to submit a preview of the branded materials to be produced to the Communication Office before printing. Also in this case, the process is not mandatory but it is advised to ensure optimal results.

